

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR VOCABULARY LEARNING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract.

This article is dedicated to describing the concept of language learning and its importance. Vocabulary learning is a long-term activity, therefore, it sometimes might cause several difficulties for language learners. There are 3 main effective methods to utilize when acquiring the vocabulary of the language in this article. Additionally, the article concentrates on the role of vocabulary learning in foreign language acquisition.

Keywords.

vocabulary, important, foreign language, acquisition, methods, effective.

Annotatsiya.

Ushbu maqola til o'rganish tushunchasi va uning ahamiyatini tavsiflashga bag'ishlangan. Lug'at o'rganish uzoq muddatli faoliyatdir, shuning uchun u ba'zida til o'rganuvchilar uchun bir qator qiyinchiliklarga olib kelishi mumkin. Ushbu maqolada tilning so'z boyligini o'zlashtirishda foydalanish uchun uchta asosiy samarali usul mavjud. Bundan tashqari, maqolada lug'atni o'rganishning chet tilini o'zlashtirishdagi roli haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar.

lug'at, muhim, chet tili, o'zlashtirish, usullar, samarali.

Аннотация.

Эта статья посвящена описанию концепции изучения языка и ее важности. Изучение словарного запаса – это долгосрочная деятельность, поэтому иногда она может вызывать определенные трудности у изучающих язык. В этой статье есть 3 основных эффективных метода, которые можно использовать при приобретении словарного запаса языка. Кроме того, в статье основное внимание уделяется роли изучения словарного запаса в овладении иностранным языком.

Ключевые слова.

словарный запас, важный, иностранный язык, овладение, приемы, эффективные.

Learning vocabulary is a crucial component of studying a second or foreign language. For a long time, memorizing vocabulary was neglected while learning a new language. But during the past few decades, the vocabulary has shifted from a peripheral to primary. The ability to communicate in a foreign language is the ultimate aim of learning for the vast majority of students. Learning vocabulary is not just helpful, but absolutely necessary in a foreign language context if you do not want to rely solely on nonverbal abilities. Moreover, increasing your vocabulary directly and favorably affects your ability to increase your overall language skills. The ideal way to learn a language effectively, however, is still unknown, in part because it depends on a wide range of conditions, and it is said that textbooks have frequently been inadequate in offering clear descriptions and instructions, perhaps it is not unexpected that professors and students have frequently been unclear about how to pursue it. Fortunately, there is now a sizable body of study on vocabulary development, even though much of it has been slow to penetrate widely used pedagogy. As much of this will be covered in this article.

Learning strategies are divided into two main categories by Oxford: direct strategies and indirect techniques. The first category includes memory and compensatory techniques, which are directly related to the target language since they call on language processing in the brain. The latter describes techniques that indirectly enhance language acquisition by creating chances, reducing fear, fostering collaboration, and in other ways, such as met cognitive, emotional, and social strategies.

O'Malley and Chamot (1986) conducted in-depth studies that offer a greater understanding of learning processes. Based on findings from cognitive psychology, they have examined learning processes and treated them as cognitive skills. According to the degree or kind of processing engaged within the information-processing model of learning, their framework distinguishes between three main categories of strategy (met, cognitive, and social/affective strategies). Higher-order executive abilities, such as met cognitive strategies, are employed by language learners to supervise, control, or steer their language acquisition. To be more precise, advanced organizers, focused attention, selective attention, self-management, delayed production, and self-evaluation are the several categories under which Met cognitive methods fall.

1. The Use of Met Cognitive Techniques

The met cognitive processes include selective attention. The majority of pupils pay closer attention to terms that are recalled or deemed to be commonly used words. The pupils frequently pay attention to specific words or types of word

knowledge, that is why selective attention is employed most frequently. This can be attributed to the techniques of instruction used by the majority of English professors. During teaching, they frequently pick out a few fundamentally significant terms and give the pupils in-depth explanations. They frequently emphasize several facets of word knowledge while teaching these terms, including collocations, numerous meanings, and grammatical qualities.

For research, the met cognitive vocabulary acquisition techniques are employed. When pupils are observed, the use of autonomy methods is at its lowest. Many students purchase vocabulary books to acquire and retain information from them. Just a small percentage of students read English newspapers or periodicals to improve their vocabulary. Fewer kids create word cards to study and recall terms whenever they have free time. This demonstrates that most subjects lack the necessary independence to learn the language. According to the interview, some students continue to look at their textbooks and the teacher's guidance in class as the primary resources for their English study. They're used to learning English in this manner. They might not understand how crucial learner autonomy is. The children were used to the instructors' directions when they were in middle school. Many found it difficult to adjust immediately to the teaching and learning styles of college after enrolling. Youngsters could still be developing the habit of independent study. While this was going on, it was discovered that kids mostly learned new terms from vocabulary books as opposed to reading things like English newspapers and periodicals.

2. The Use of Cognitive Techniques

The most popular techniques are the cognitive ones. One of the cognitive methods is the use of dictionaries. That is the one that gets utilized the most. The majority of disciplines often use dictionaries. Many pupils pay close attention to any predetermined idioms or phrases that go along with the word they are looking up. The majority of students not only look up new terms they come across for meaning but also check up on words they have already learned for more precise use or verification. Fewer pupils focus attention on both the English and Chinese explanations of a term when they are searching it up. The approach of using a dictionary is common throughout the disciplines. The findings indicate that a bilingual dictionary is the most widely used. The current study also came to a similar conclusion that using a dictionary might help you learn new terms or broaden your vocabulary.

The participants can believe that acquiring language using a dictionary is the fastest and most effective method. They could locate highly precise definitions of

new words, helpful expressions and fixed phrases, sentences using those words, and even images of words in dictionaries. They lack a real conversational setting in which to pick up terminology.

3. Using Social/Affective Techniques

Besides these two ways, students also use other methods to learn vocabulary. Some of them claimed that they would motivate themselves to continue their studies if the results of their vocabulary acquisition were unsatisfactory. As we all know, students are increasingly conscious of the need of boosting their self-esteem, encourage themselves and control worry.

This can also be a result of Chinese cultural impact. At a very young age, the pupils have been taught how to manage themselves. In contrast, just a small number of kids visit the English area and try to utilize as many of the new terms as they can. Fewer people actively seek out and never pass up the chance to speak English with foreigners.

To sum up, vocabulary learning comprises both the capacity to utilize vocabulary appropriately and the mastery of a specific number of words or phrases. Correct vocabulary acquisition techniques are therefore crucial for pupils' vocabulary acquisition, particularly vocabulary memorization. As we know, the foundation of learning a language is vocabulary therefore each student should make an effort to identify one or more effective strategies that work for them to increase their vocabulary and advance their English learning. Every form of vocabulary-learning strategy has great value and utility that the benefits of these approaches should be realized by language learners, who should then employ them optimally depending on their circumstances.

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